

Time model

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Abstract

Time has two basic characteristics, liquidity and locality. Time flows all the time, and the time of different systems is different. By constructing an absolute space-time framework, we coordinate the mobility and locality of time. We believe that time is the state and result of the system moving in the absolute space-time framework.

Introduction

What's the time? This is an old problem. Newton put forward absolute space-time and emphasized the absoluteness of time flow. Einstein put forward relative space-time and emphasized the difference of time flow. Their views each focus on a feature of time. Moreover, they all contain the same point in their views, movement. Einstein further suggested that there was a special connection between time and space. Through the integration of these points, we get the exact concept of time. As for the derivation of concepts, the most important thing is to understand the relationship between time and space. The space passed is the time passed. Motion generation time. Matter produces motion.

On the fluidity of time

Time has fluidity, which indicates movement. Einstein suggested that motion has relativity. Newton suggested that time is absolute. Therefore, we assume that there is an absolute space-time framework in the universe. It is an absolute reference system. All systems are moving relative to the absolute space-time frame. A system can be a particle, a spaceship, a planet, or a galaxy. Absolute space-time frame includes three-dimensional space frame and three-dimensional time frame, which are integrated. We believe that the space that the system passes through in the absolute space-time framework is the elapsed time. This time is called absolute time. The distance of the system in the absolute space-time framework is the absolute time. Absolute time can explain the fluidity of time.

On the locality of time

Each system has its own local time. Only local time is meaningful to the system. Different systems often have different local time. The tool for measuring time is a timer. The timer is a local periodic motion. Therefore, the local time is defined by some local periodic motion. For example, the time of a spacecraft is defined by the clock it carries. Local means in the same system. We assume that all parts of the same

system have the same motion state. (below a certain accuracy, we believe that all parts have the same motion state) Obviously, the local time of the system is consistent. For example, a spaceship has two clocks, clock A and clock B, They are exactly the same and work properly. Then they display the same time. A and B go the same distance in the same cycle, so they pass the same absolute time. Figure 1

Fig. 1. The local time in a system is consistent.

For the same reason, the local time of different systems is different. If their motion states are different, they will pass through different absolute times. For example, two cars move at different speeds, and the car carries clock A and clock B respectively. A and B are exactly the same and work properly. Assuming that the rate of A is greater than that of B, when clock A and clock B run the same cycle respectively, the distance of clock A is greater than that of clock B. Figure 2

Fig. 2. Different systems go through the same period, but different absolute time.

Therefore, after the same local time, the absolute time of A is greater than that of B. In other words, doing the same thing, A takes more absolute time than B. So clock A looks slower than clock B. Moreover, the local time of the system is consistent, so everything in system A seems to be slower than system B. Different motion states lead to different local time.

Conclusion

- 1 Time: In the absolute space-time framework, the state and result of system motion.
- 2 Absolute time: The distance the system passes in the absolute space-time framework.
- 3 Local time: The time determined by a certain periodic movement in the system is local time.

Some questions about time

1 Go back to the past and stop time

These two things cannot be done. No matter what state the system moves in, the total distance traveled by the system in the absolute space-time framework cannot be reduced. The total distance can only be increased. The difference between different systems is that the distance increases fast and slow. This increase can be close to zero, but not zero. If the increase is zero, the system is absolutely stationary, without any interaction with other systems, it will not exist in the universe. Therefore, the arrow of time cannot turn back or stop.

2 Accelerate to the future

It can be done. Methods include: Extend local cycles, such as hibernation, into high gravity areas; high speed movement, such as boarding a spacecraft and flying at high speed.

3 Decelerate forward

It can be done. Methods include: Shorten the local cycle, such as accelerating metabolism and entering low gravity areas; reduce the speed of movement, such as getting off a spaceship.

4 Start and end of time

Matter produces motion, and motion produces time. If matter is eternal, time is eternal.

Thanks to Newton's absolute space - time and Einstein's relative space - time.